

Physico-Chemical Variability of Alfisols with and without Concretions Developed in Sandstones within Eastern Kogi State of Nigeria

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Abstract: This study investigated the physico-chemical variability of Alfisols with and without redox concentrations developed in sandstones within Dekina Local Government area of Kogi State, Nigeria. The research through reconnaissance identified two pedons at Okowowolo (Alf₁) and Abocho (Alf₂) with and without redoximorphic features. Soil profiles were dug using spade and digger, and interpreted following the standard of United States Department of Agriculture (USDA) for Field Description. Soil samples were collected in labelled polyethylene bags and core samplers for the physico-chemical analyses. Results revealed that the coarse and fine sand fractions were higher at the surface with respective mean values of 540 and 230 g kg⁻¹, than in the subsurface soils with mean values of 483 and 207 g kg⁻¹. The silt proportion had a mean of 60 g kg⁻¹ at the surface and a mean value of 70 g kg⁻¹ in the subsurface soils. The clay proportion was lower at the surface soils with a range from 100 to 240 g kg⁻¹ (mean: 170 g kg⁻¹) than in the subsurface soils with a mean of 240 g kg⁻¹. T-test revealed statistical significant difference with respect to coarse sand, silt and clay which have respective surface and subsurface *p*-values of 0.001, 0.012 and 0.001 at 95% confidence interval. The soils' cation exchange capacity percentage base saturation also indicated statistically significant difference among the soils with respective *p*-values of 0.005 and 0.039, at 95% confidence interval. The study concluded that alfisols in Kogi State have different physico-chemical properties that influence its fertility.

Keywords: Alfisols, Bulk density, Concretions, Sandstones, Soil pH

Introduction

According to Soil Survey Staff (1999), the central concept of *Alfisols* is that of soils that have ochric epipedon, an argillic horizon, and moderate to high base saturation and in which water is held at less than 1500 kPa tension during at least 3 months each year when the soils are warm enough for plants to grow. As documented in Akamigbo (2010), *Alfisols* possess unique properties of a combination of an ochric or umbric epipedon, an argillic or nitric horizon, a medium to high supply of bases in the soils (> 35% base saturation), and water available to mesophilic plants for more than half of the year. Due to the good fertility and hydrologic condition of *Alfisols*, they are often intensively used (Ibid). Many studies have been undertaken to assess the status of *Alfisols* in Nigeria. These studies include the baseline fertility survey of a gravelly *Alfisols* in Kwara State which was carried out with a view to identifying soil health constraints and site-specific sustainable land management practices for optimizing crop production by Adegbite *et al.* (2020). The study revealed that the soils are very fragile and poor in native fertility. Also, the fertility status of *Alfisols* in the Gubi soil series in Bauchi State was evaluated by Voncir *et al.* (2006). It was reported that the soils were generally slightly acid to moderately acid with the pH being significantly higher in the lower horizons than in the surface horizons. The study also revealed that the exchangeable bases were

high to medium while the Cation Exchange Capacity (CEC) was medium to high.

Concretions in soils are cemented bodies of Fe-Mn oxides (Schoeneberger *et al.*, 2012). They are redoximorphic features expressed by localized zones of enhanced pigmentation due to an accrual of, or a phase change in, the Fe-Mn minerals; or physical accumulation of Fe-Mn minerals (redox concentrations) (Ibid). The progressive formation of concretions in laterite weathering profiles can be traced from the mottled subsurface horizons to the surface while concretions result from the physical breakup of iron (Fe) (Bourman 1993). The concretions are considered the largest Fe reservoir in the surficial soils and sediments (Löhr *et al.*, 2010).

The classification of soils in eastern Kogi state of Nigeria by Ukabiala (2019) revealed the occurrence of two profiles (*Alfisols*) within same parent material. In one of the profiles were observed concretions while the other had none. There is few or no research so far that specifically outlined the variability in the fertility characteristics between these types of profiles. Hence, this aroused the researchers' curiosity to study if there are significant differences in the physical and chemical properties these *Alfisols* with and without concretions, occurring on same lithology. Therefore the objective of this research is to determine the physico-chemical variability of *Alfisols* with and without redox concentrations developed in

sandstones within Dekina local government area of Kogi state, Nigeria.

Materials and Methods

Study area

The study area was conducted within the eastern zone of Kogi State. Kogi State in turn is situated within the middle belt of Nigeria. It lies within latitudes 6°51'N to 7°54'N and longitudes 6°45'E to 7°38'E with altitude ranging from 38 to 426 m above mean sea level (Ukabiala, 2019). Within Kogi east, the study site was in Dekina Local Government Area. The profiles were sited at Okowowolo (Alf₁) and Abocho (Alf₂). The soil profiles, Alf₁ and Alf₂ were profiles with concretions and without concretions, respectively. The landscape generally is gently to undulating plain having a range of 1 to 4 percent slope (Ukabiala, 2019). The soils were well drained with slight vulnerabilities to erosion hazard.

Climate of the study area

There are two distinct seasons in the study which are rainy season and dry season. The rainy season lasts from April to October while the dry season is observed between November and March (Weatherbase, 2011). There is also a very dusty and cold period as a result of the North-east winds which bring about the harmattan. This zone has an annual rainfall ranging from 1100 to 1300 mm with a mean of 1200 mm per annum. The average monthly temperature varies between 17 and 36°C (Amhakhian and Osemwota, 2012). The highest temperature (36°C) has been

recorded during the dry season (Ukabiala, 2019). The mean relative humidity is lowest during the dry season and highest during the rainy season of the years, giving 15 and 67% respectively (Ukabiala, 2019).

Vegetation and land use in the study area

The study was undertaken within the rain forest belt found in the southern guinea savannah (Keay, 1959). There are rich deciduous which are occasionally stunted trees such as Iroko and Mahogany tree. These are found within the rain forest. The Guinea Savannah belt is characterized by tall grasses and some trees. The land is open during the dry season with charred trees and remains of burnt grasses. The trees common in the area include Locust bean, Shea butter tree and Oil bean. Among the common crops cultivated in the area are cassava, yam, maize and groundnut.

Geology of the study area

The soils of the study area have been reported to have developed from rocks with low silica (SiO₂) but high iron (Fe) content (Ukabiala (2019) also reported dominance of false-bedded keana sandstones (Plate 1) within the study area.

Field work

Soil samples were carefully collected from two soil profile pits (Alf₁ and Alf₂ (Figure 1). The soil samples were collected from each identified soil horizon. The collected samples were properly packed into well-labelled polyethene bags for laboratory analyses. Also, core samples were collected from pre-

determined depths of 0 – 25, 25 – 50 and 50 – 75 cm for the analysis of some soil physical properties (Bulk density, Total porosity and Saturated hydraulic conductivity).

Laboratory Analyses

The soil samples collected from the field were air-dried in the laboratory and later sieved with a sieve of 2 mm mesh size.

Figure 1 Map of Kogi State showing sampling locations

Plate 1 An excavation site in Kogi East exposing soil parent material (False-bedded Kaena Sandstone)
Source: Ukabiala (2019)

Analyses of some soil physical characteristics

The particle size distribution (PSD) < 2 mm was determined using Bouyoucos Hydrometer method as described by Gee and Or (2002). Sodium hydroxide was used as dispersant. The textural classes were read out from the USDA soil textural triangle. The Bulk density was determined by the core methods described by Landon (1981).

$$Bulk\ Density = \frac{Oven\ dry\ weight\ of\ soil}{Volume\ of\ Soil} \dots (1)$$

Soil porosity was calculated with the values of the bulk density using the method outlined by Brady and Weil (2002).

$$Total\ Porosity = \frac{Bulk\ Density \times 100}{Particle\ Density} \dots (2)$$

The Soil Saturated Hydraulic Conductivity (K_{sat}) was determined based on Klute and Dirksen (1986) method and calculated by using the transposed Darcy's equation for vertical flows of liquids;

$$K_{sat} = \frac{Q/At}{L/DH} \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

where K_{sat} is the saturated hydraulic conductivity ($cm\ h^{-1}$), Q is steady-state volume of water outflow from the entire soil column (cm^3), A is the cross-section area (cm^2), t is the time interval (h), L is length of the sample (cm), and DH is the change in the hydraulic head (cm).

Analyses of some soil chemical characteristics

Soil pH was determined in water and 1N KCl solution using a soil solution ratio of 1:2.5 with the aid of a glass electrode pH meter (McLean, 1982). Organic carbon was determined by wet dichromate acid oxidation method (Nelson and Sommers, 1982). Total nitrogen was estimated by the macro-kjeldahl digestion method (Bremmer and Mulvaney, 1982). Available phosphorus was obtained using Bray II bicarbonate extraction method

(Olsen and Sommers, 1982), using 0.03 N ammonium fluoride with 0.1N HCl. The phosphorus in the extract was determined with a photo-electric colorimeter. Exchangeable bases (Ca, Mg, K and Na) were extracted with 1N NH₄OAc (pH 7.0) using 1:10 soil solution ratio. Potassium and sodium in the extract were determined with Flame Photometer while Ca and Mg were determined by atomic absorption titrated with 0.05 NaOH to a permanent pink end point using phenolphthalein indicator. Total exchangeable bases (TEB) were obtained by the summation of the exchangeable bases (Na, K, Ca and Mg) (Rhoades, 1982). The cation exchange capacity of the soils was determined with 1N NH₄OAc, pH 7.0 (Rhoades, 1982). The effective cation exchange capacity of the soil samples was estimated by the summation of the exchangeable bases and the exchangeable acidity (Rhoades, 1982);

$$ECEC = Ca^{2+} + Mg^{2+} + K^{+} + Na^{+} + EA \quad \dots\dots\dots(5)$$

The percentage base saturation was derived by dividing the total exchangeable bases (Ca, Mg, K and Na) by the CEC obtained and multiplying by 100 (Rhoades, 1982);

$$PBS = \frac{Ca^{2+} + Mg^{2+} + K^{+} + Na^{+} \times 100}{CEC} \quad \dots\dots\dots(6)$$

Aluminium saturation percentage (ASP) was obtained by multiplying the ratio of

spectrophotometry (Thomas, 1982). Exchangeable sodium percentage (ESP) was calculated using the standard of Soil Survey Staff (1999) formula:

$$ESP = \frac{\text{Exchangeable sodium} \times 100}{CEC} \quad \dots\dots\dots(4)$$

The titration method which was outlined in by Thomas (1982) was adopted in the determination of the exchangeable acidity. The samples were extracted with 1N KCl solution and the extract aluminium concentration and ECEC with 100 (Soil Survey Staff, 1999);

$$ASP = \frac{Al \times 100}{ECEC} \quad \dots\dots\dots(7)$$

The results of the physical and chemical analyses were interpreted using standard ratings (Enwezor *et al.*, 1989; Soil Survey Staff, 1999; Shehu *et al.*, 2015).

Statistical Analysis

The data generated from the laboratory analyses were put to descriptive statistics, while the independent-samples T-test analysis was used to make statistical comparison between selected physical and chemical properties of the two soils. Both analyses were done using the Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS), version 20. This alpha (α) level was set at 0.05, which means that if the *p*-value is less than 0.05 (i.e., *p*<0.05), the result was declared statistically significant. Alternatively, if the *p*-value is greater than 0.05 (i.e., *p*>0.05), the result was declared not statistically significant.

Results and Discussion

Physical characteristics of the soils

Some physical parameters of the soils studied presented in Tables 1 and 2. The coarse and fine sand fractions were higher at the surface with respective mean value of 540 and 230 g kg⁻¹, than in the subsurface soils with mean value of 483 and 207 g kg⁻¹. The silt proportion had a mean of 60 g kg⁻¹ at the surface and a mean value of 70 g kg⁻¹ in the subsurface soils. The clay proportion was lower at the surface soils with a range from 100 to 240 g kg⁻¹ (mean: 170 g kg⁻¹) than in the subsurface soils with a mean of 240 g kg⁻¹. These proportions gave rise to textural classes ranging from loamy sand, sandy clay, clay loam to sandy clay loam in both surface and subsurface soils of this mapping unit. The respective mean value of the silt/clay ratio was 0.40 and 0.32 at the surface and subsurface soils. The bulk density of the surface soils ranged from 1.39 to 1.55 g cm⁻³ (mean: 1.47 g cm⁻³) while the subsurface soils had a range of 1.50 to 1.80 g cm⁻³ with a mean value of 1.66 g cm⁻³. The percentage total porosity ranged from 41.51 to 42.55% with a mean value of 44.53% at the surface soils while the values obtained at the subsurface soils ranged from 35.47 to 43.40% with a mean value of 37.27%. The values of saturated hydraulic conductivity ranged from 86.25 to 111.31 cm hr⁻¹ at the surface soils, and 86.25 to 131.55 cm hr⁻¹ at the subsurface with mean values of 118.90 and 115.17 cm hr⁻¹ respectively.

The comparison between the soils two profiles using T-test revealed statistical significant difference with respect to coarse sand, silt and clay with respective p-values of 0.001, 0.012 and 0.001 at 95% confidence interval. However, there was no significant statistical difference between the soils with respect to fine sand and silt:clay, as the respective p-values, 0.242 and 0.082 are higher than 0.05. Furthermore, the T-test analysis showed no significant statistical difference between the means of the values of soil bulk density, total porosity and hydraulic conductivity which had respective p-values of 0.789, 0.799 and 0.252 at 95% confidence interval.

The presence of Fe-Mn concretions dominant in the Alf₁ pedon is an indication of redox concentrations in the soil layers. Similar redoximorphic features occurred in a Fine, Mixed, Semiactive, Isohyperthermic Typic Haplustalfs located at Killikulam Agriculture College, India but on a lower landscape of elevation, 23 m above mean sea level (Soil Survey Staff, 1999).

The redox concentration may have contributed to the significant variation in proportions of the coarse sand, silt and clay since the p-values were lower than 0.05. However, the no significance differences observed in the soils' hydraulic conductivity, porosity and bulk density may be attributed to presence of concretions that created large diameter pores. According to Gardner *et al.* (1999), values of hydraulic conductivity

range between about 10^{-3} m s^{-1} and $5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ ms}^{-1}$ at saturation in sandy soils. The implication of presence of macropores is that there could be substantial increase in rates of movement of soluble pollutants from soils (White, 1986).

Chemical characteristics of the soils

Table 3 shows the chemical characteristics of the soils of the study area. The pH in H₂O and KCl are higher at the surface soils (ranges: 5.0 to 5.8 and 4.0 to 4.9) than in the subsurface soils (range: 4.7 to 5.0 and 3.6 to 4.0) respectively. The organic carbon (OC) and total nitrogen (TN) of these soils were irregularly distributed among the depths. The finding is in consistent with the report of Ukabiala and Obazi (2022).

Table 1 Textural characteristics of soils of the study area

Pedon/ Coordinate	Location	Depth (cm)	Horizon designation	Coarse	Fine	Silt	Clay	Silt:Clay	Texture
				sand	sand				
Alf ₁ 07°34'35.8"N 006°03'30.1"E	Okowowolo	0-15	Ap1	420	270	70	240	0.29	scl
		15-35	Apc	360	210	110	320	0.34	scl
		35-70	Btc1	360	170	70	400	0.18	cl
		70-110	Btc2	440	90	110	360	0.31	sc
Alf ₂ 07°34'13.7"N 006°59'47.0"E	Abocho	0-18	Ap1	660	190	50	100	0.50	ls
		18-37	Ap2	540	270	50	140	0.36	sl
		37-85	B1	600	270	30	100	0.30	ls
		85-190	B2	600	230	50	120	0.42	ls
Surface range				420-660	190-270	50-70	100-240	0.29-0.50	
Subsurface range				360-600	90-270	30-110	100-400	0.18-0.42	
Surface mean				540	230	60	170	0.40	ls
Subsurface mean				483	207	70	240	0.32	scl
<i>p</i> -value				0.001	0.242	0.012	0.001	0.082	

ls= loamy sand, sl= sandy loam, cl= clay loam, sc= sandy clay, scl= sandy clay loam, Ap – Soil surface horizon with tillage disturbance, Btc = Subsurface horizon with accumulation of silicate clay and concretions, Apc = Surface horizon with tillage disturbance and concretions, B = Subsurface horizon

p-value, "Sig. (2-tailed)"

Confidence interval = 95%

Values in green depict significant statistical difference

Table 2 Some physical characteristics of the soils

Pedon/Coordinate	Location	Depth (cm)	Bulk density (g cm⁻³)	Total porosity (%)	K_{sat} (cm hr⁻¹)
Alf ₁ 07°34'35.8"N 006°03'30.1"E	Okowowolo	0-25	1.55	41.51	111.31
		25-50	1.50	43.40	126.49
		50-75	1.80	32.08	86.25
Alf ₂ 07°34'35.8"N 006°03'30.1"E	Abocho	0-25	1.39	47.55	126.49
		25-50	1.64	38.11	131.55
		50-75	1.71	35.47	116.37
Surface range			1.39-1.55	41.51-47.55	86.25-111.31
Subsurface range			1.50-1.80	35.47-43.40	86.25-131.55
Surface mean			1.47	44.53	118.90
Subsurface mean			1.66	37.27	115.17
<i>p</i> -value			0.798	0.799	0.252

K_{sat}= Saturated hydraulic conductivity

p-value, "Sig. (2-tailed)", Confidence interval = 95%,

The surface soils had mean value of 12.40 g kg⁻¹ (OC) and 1.80 g kg⁻¹ (TN) while 6.10 g kg⁻¹ (OC) and 0.90 g kg⁻¹ (TN) were obtained in the subsurface soils. The carbon and nitrogen ratio ranged from 5 to 8 and 3 to 12 in the surface and subsurface soils respectively. Available phosphorus values were higher at the subsurface soils (mean: 3.11 mg kg⁻¹) than at the surface soils (mean: 1.87 mg kg⁻¹). Exchangeable calcium and magnesium dominated the exchange sites with mean values of 6.00 and 1.20 cmol_c kg⁻¹ in the surface soils, 4.45 and 1.07 cmol_c kg⁻¹ in the subsurface soils, respectively. Similar observation was made by Ukabiala(2022). The exchangeable acidity predominated by the exchangeable hydrogen and aluminium had a higher mean value (2.20 cmol_c kg⁻¹) at the subsurface than at the surface soils (1.3 cmol_c kg⁻¹). The mean value of cation

exchange capacity of 10.45 and 10.57 cmol_c kg⁻¹ was obtained at the surface and subsurface soils, respectively. The mean percentage base saturation was 74% at the surface soils as well as 57% in the subsurface soils. The exchangeable sodium percentage values were higher (mean: 0.60%) at the surface soils than at the subsurface soils (mean: 0.31%). The aluminium saturation percentage of the soils varied between 0 and 10% with a mean value of 7% at the surface soils while in the subsurface soils, it ranged from 8 to 16% with a mean value of 11%. Ukabiala *et al.* (2022) made a similar observation.

Table 3 Chemical characteristics of the soils

Peon/ Coordinate	Location	Depth (cm)	Horizon designation	pH		OC (g kg ⁻¹)	TN	C:N	Av. P (mg kg ⁻¹)	Exchangeable cations (cmol. kg ⁻¹)					
				(H ₂ O)	(KCl)					Ca ²⁺	Mg ²⁺	K ⁺	Na ⁺	H ⁺	Al ³⁺
Alf ₁ 07°34'35.8"N 006°03'30.1"E	Okowowolo	0-15	Ap1	5.0	4.0	15.6	1.90	8	1.87	4.00	2.00	0.10	0.07	0.80	0.80
		15-35	Apc	4.9	3.6	12.7	1.10	12	3.73	4.20	1.00	0.07	0.04	2.40	0.80
		35-70	Btc1	4.7	3.7	6.60	0.70	9	2.80	4.20	1.60	0.07	0.04	1.20	1.40
		70-110	Btc2	4.8	3.7	2.90	0.90	3	1.87	4.30	1.00	0.05	0.02	1.80	0.60
Alf ₂ 07°34'13.7"N 006°59'47.0"E	Abocho	0-18	Ap1	5.8	4.9	9.20	1.70	5	1.87	8.00	0.40	0.09	0.05	1.00	-
		18-37	Ap2	4.9	3.8	6.20	1.10	6	4.66	6.00	1.40	0.07	0.04	1.60	0.40
		37-85	B1	5.0	4.0	5.00	1.30	4	2.80	4.00	0.20	0.05	0.02	1.00	0.60
		85-190	B2	4.8	3.7	4.50	0.40	11	2.80	4.00	1.20	0.05	0.02	1.40	-
Surface range				5.0-5.8	4.0-4.9	9.20-15.6	1.70-1.90	5-8	-	4.00-8.00	0.40-2.00	0.09-0.10	0.05-0.07	0.80-1.00	-
Subsurface range				4.7-5.0	3.6-4.0	2.90-12.7	0.40-1.30	3-12	1.87-4.66	4.00-6.00	0.20-1.60	0.05-0.07	0.02-0.04	1.00-2.40	0.40-1.40
Surface mean				5.4	4.45	12.40	1.80	7	1.87	6.00	1.20	0.09	0.06	0.90	0.80
Subsurface mean				4.9	3.75	6.10	0.90	8	3.11	4.45	1.07	0.06	0.03	1.57	0.76
Surface p-value				0.291	0.269	0.333	0.949	0.560	0.550	0.217	0.168	0.613	0.463	0.461	0.208

OC= Organic carbon, TN= Total Nitrogen, Av. P= Available Phosphorus, Ca²⁺= Exchangeable Calcium, Mg²⁺= Exchangeable Magnesium⁺, K= Exchangeable Potassium, Na⁺= Exchangeable Sodium, H⁺= Exchangeable Hydrogen, Al³⁺= Exchangeable Aluminium, Ap – Soil surface horizon with tillage disturbance, Btc = Subsurface horizon with accumulation of silicate clay and concretions, Apc = Surface horizon with tillage disturbance and concretions, B = Subsurface horizon, (*p*-value) ("Sig. (2-tailed)"), Confidence interval = 95%,

Table 3 Continued

Peon/Coordinate	Location	Depth (cm)	Horizon designation	EA	CEC	ECEC	TEB	PBS	ESP	ASP
				(cmol _c kg ⁻¹)				(%)		
Alf ₁ 07°34'35.8"N 006°03'30.1"E	Okowowolo	0-15	Ap1	1.60	12.00	7.77	6.17	51	0.58	10
		15-35	Apc	3.20	15.60	8.51	5.31	34	0.26	9
		35-70	Btc1	2.60	11.20	8.51	5.91	53	0.36	16
		70-110	Btc2	2.40	12.00	7.77	5.37	45	0.17	8
Alf ₂ 07°34'13.7"N 006°59'47.0"E	Abocho	0-18	Ap1	1.00	8.90	9.54	8.54	96	0.61	-
		18-37	Ap2	2.00	8.20	9.51	7.51	92	0.61	4
		37-85	B1	1.60	8.20	5.87	4.27	52	0.24	10
		85-190	B2	1.40	8.20	6.67	5.27	64	0.24	-
Surface range				1.0-1.6	8.90-12.00	7.77-9.54	6.17-8.54	51-96	0.58-0.61	0-10
Subsurface range				1.40-3.20	8.20-15.60	5.87-9.51	4.27-7.51	34-92	0.17-0.61	8-16
Surface mean				1.30	10.45	8.66	7.36	74	0.60	7
Subsurface mean				2.20	10.57	7.81	5.61	57	0.31	11
<i>p</i> -value				0.051	0.005	0.812	0.508	0.039	0.573	0.314

- = No significant value EA= Exchangeable acidity, CEC= Cation exchange capacity, ECEC= Effective Cation Exchange Capacity, TEB= Total Exchangeable Bases, PBS= Percentage Base Saturation, ESP= Exchangeable Sodium Percentage, ASP= Aluminium Saturation Percentage, Ap – Soil surface horizon with tillage disturbance, Btc = Subsurface horizon with accumulation of silicate clay and concretions, Apc = Surface horizon with tillage disturbance and concretions, B = Subsurface horizon

(*p*-value) ("Sig. (2-tailed)")

Confidence interval = 95%

Values in green depict significant statistical difference

The T-test analysis revealed that among the chemical characteristics, only cation exchange capacity and percentage base saturation were significantly statistically different among the two soils, having *p*-values of 0.005 and 0.039 at 95% confidence interval. On the hand, the T-test result revealed no significant statistical difference between the soils' pH (H₂O), pH (KCl). Total nitrogen, organic carbon, exchangeable calcium, nitrogen ratio, available phosphorus, magnesium, potassium, sodium, hydrogen, aluminium and acidity, effective cation exchange capacity, total exchangeable bases, exchangeable sodium percentage and aluminium saturation percentage which have respective *p*-values of 0.291, 0.269, 0.333, 0.949, 0.560, 0.550, 0.217, 0.168, 0.613, 0.463, 0.461, 0.208, 0.051, 0.812, 0.508, 0.573 and 0.314 which are higher than 0.05 at 95% confidence interval.

The pH (H₂O) of the soils ranged from very strongly to strongly acid with higher pH in the surface than in the subsurface soils which could infer a significant amount of exchangeable aluminium (Buol *et al.*, 1973). According to Kamprath (1967), this condition may affect plant growth significantly. Similar result was reported by Onyekanna *et al.* (2012) for soils of Ideato North Local Government Area of Imo state. Onyekanna and his team reported that the high acidic nature of soils could be attributed to high intensity rainfall which leaches basic cations down the profile.

This pedogenic process of leaching would have also led to the low levels of total nitrogen and the exchangeable cations recorded for soils of 19c mapping unit. The CEC of the soils are low but a moderate level of 15.60 cmol_c kg⁻¹ was encountered in a subsurface layer which may be attributed to the moderate high silt and clay content of the horizon. However, CEC of most soils increased with pH which means that at very low pH values, the CEC is generally low (Brady and Weil, 2002). Furthermore, the soil pH (H₂O) is significantly lower in the profile with concretions than the profile without concretions both in the surface and subsurface soils, but was only observed in the subsurface soils through pH (KCl). The significant difference observed on CEC and PBS may be attributed to the possible variation in the surface area of the soil particles due to concretions.

Conclusion and Recommendation

The study concluded that alfisols in Kogi State have different physico-chemical properties. The coarse and fine sand fractions were higher at the surface than in the subsurface. The silt proportion at the surface is slightly lower than those in the subsurface. Similarly, the clay proportion was lower at the surface soils than in the subsurface. Also, there was difference in soils' cation exchange capacity percentage base saturation among the coarse sand, silt and clay soils. Thus, the

nutrients availability and fertility of this soil is influenced by these characteristics. Hence, it is recommended that soil test should be undertaken to determine the suitable crops to be grown in that part of the State.

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